

Stable Andrews-Curtis trivialization of AK(3) revisited.

A case study using automated deduction.

(preprint)

Alexei Lisitsa
University of Liverpool
email: a.lisitsa@liverpool.ac.uk

Abstract

Recent work by Shehper et al. (2024) demonstrated that the well-known Akbulut-Kirby AK(3) balanced presentation of the trivial group is stably AC-equivalent to the trivial presentation. This result eliminates AK(3) as a potential counterexample to the stable Andrews-Curtis conjecture. In this paper, we present an alternative proof of this result using an automated deduction approach. We provide several transformation sequences, derived from two different proofs generated by the automated theorem prover Prover9, that certify the stable AC-equivalence of AK(3) and the trivial presentation. We conclude by proposing a challenge to develop computational methods for searching stable AC-transformations.

1 Introduction

The Andrews-Curtis conjecture (ACC) [3] is a well-known open problem in combinatorial group theory deeply linked with the questions in low-dimensional topology. ACC states that every balanced presentation of the trivial group can be transformed into a trivial presentation by a sequence of simple transformations.

Several computational methods have been suggested for efficiently searching for such simplifications (e.g. [5, 13, 16, 7, 6, 9, 15]). However, there are

still infinite sets of balanced trivial group presentations that could serve as potential counterexamples to the conjecture, for which the necessary simplifications have not yet been discovered.

For a group presentation $\langle x_1, \dots, x_n; r_1, \dots, r_m \rangle$ with generators x_i , and relators r_j , consider the following transformations.

AC1 Replace some r_i by r_i^{-1} .

AC2 Replace some r_i by $r_i \cdot r_j$, $j \neq i$.

AC3 Replace some r_i by $w \cdot r_i \cdot w^{-1}$ where w is any word in the generators.

AC4 Introduce a new generator y and relator y or delete a generator y and relator y .

Two presentations g and g' are called *Andrews-Curtis equivalent* (*AC-equivalent*) if one of them can be obtained from the other by applying a finite sequence of transformations of the types (AC1) - (AC3). Two presentations are stably AC-equivalent if one of them can be obtained from the other by applying a finite sequence of transformations of the types (AC1)–(AC4). A presentation $\langle x_1, \dots, x_n; r_1, \dots, r_m \rangle$ is called *balanced* if $n = m$. A balanced presentation is called *AC-simplifiable*, or *AC-trivializable*, if it is equivalent to trivial presentation $\langle x_1, \dots, x_n; x_1, \dots, x_n \rangle$.

Conjecture 1 (Andrews-Curtis [3]) *If $\langle x_1, \dots, x_n; r_1, \dots, r_n \rangle$ is a balanced presentation*

of the trivial group it is AC-equivalent to the trivial presentation $\langle x_1, \dots, x_n; x_1, \dots, x_n \rangle$

The stable version of the conjecture asserts that every balanced presentation of a trivial group is stably AC-equivalent (i.e., transformations using AC4 are permitted) to the trivial presentation. Both versions of the conjecture remain unresolved and present significant challenges.

1.1 Akbulut-Kirby presentations

The infinite sequence of possible counterexamples was first introduced in [1], where the authors defined an infinite family of balanced Akbulut-Kirby presentations of the trivial group: $\text{AK}(n) = \langle a, b \mid a^n b^{-(n+1)}, abab^{-1}a^{-1}b^{-1} \rangle$, $n \geq 2$.

The presentation $\text{AK}(2)$ was shown to be AC-trivializable and, therefore, is not a counterexample, as demonstrated in [13]. The AC-trivializability of all $\text{AK}(n)$ for $n > 2$ remains an open problem, with $\text{AK}(3)$ being the shortest and perhaps most well-known potential counterexample to the AC conjecture. The same was true for the stable AC-trivializability of $\text{AK}(n)$ for $n > 2$ until August 2024, when it was shown in [15] that $\text{AK}(3)$ is *stably* trivializable. The result was established by identifying a sequence of "non-stable" AC-moves that transform a presentation, known from [2] to be stably AC-simplifiable, into $\text{AK}(3)$. This sequence was discovered using a greedy search algorithm, which was developed as part of a broader effort to study search and reinforcement learning algorithms in the context of the Andrews-Curtis conjecture, as detailed in [15].

1.2 Contributions

In this communication, we present alternative proofs of the stable AC-trivializability of $\text{AK}(3)$ using our approach based on automated deduction [8, 9, 10] to identify the necessary reduction sequences. We provide five distinct transformation sequences, based on different subsets of AC-moves, each derived from two separate proofs obtained using the automated theorem prover Prover9 [12]. Additionally, we compare

our solutions with that in [15] and highlight the challenge of developing computational methods for the efficient search of stable simplifications.

2 Automated theorem proving for AC-simplifications

In [8, 9, 10, 11], we developed an approach that utilizes automated deduction in first-order logic to search for trivializations, demonstrating that it is highly competitive. In this approach, we formalized AC-transformations—typically presented at the meta-level—at the object level, using term rewriting modulo group theory and first-order deduction. This section provides a brief overview of our approach.

Let T_G be the equational theory of groups. For each $n \geq 2$ we formulate [9] a natural term rewriting system modulo T_G , which captures AC-transformations of presentations of dimension n . For $n = 2$ that proceeds as follows. For an alphabet $A = \{a_1, a_2\}$ a term rewriting system ACT_2 consists of the following rules:

$$\mathbf{R1L} \quad f(x, y) \rightarrow f(r(x), y)$$

$$\mathbf{R1R} \quad f(x, y) \rightarrow f(x, r(y))$$

$$\mathbf{R2L} \quad f(x, y) \rightarrow f(x \cdot y, y)$$

$$\mathbf{R2R} \quad f(x, y) \rightarrow f(x, y \cdot x)$$

$$\mathbf{R3L}_i \quad f(x, y) \rightarrow f((a_i \cdot x) \cdot r(a_i), y) \text{ for } a_i \in A, i = 1, 2$$

$$\mathbf{R3R}_i \quad f(x, y) \rightarrow f(x, (a_i \cdot y) \cdot r(a_i)) \text{ for } a_i \in A, i = 1, 2$$

The rewrite relations \rightarrow_{ACT} for ACT_2 and $\rightarrow_{ACT/G}$ for ACT modulo theory T_G on the set of all terms are defined in the standard way [4]. The notion of rewrite relation $\rightarrow_{ACT/G}$ captures adequately the notion of AC-rewriting, that is for presentations p_1 and p_2 we have $p_1 \rightarrow_{AC}^* p_2$ iff $t_{p_1} \rightarrow_{ACT/G}^* t_{p_2}$. Here t_p denotes a term encoding of a presentation p , that is for $p = \langle a_1, a_2 \mid t_1, t_2 \rangle$ we have $t_p = f(t_1, t_2)$.

The term rewriting system ACT_2 can be simplified to the following reduced term rewriting system $rACT_2$ [9] without changing the transitive closure

non-ground axiom **I-R3Z** was included in the assumptions, the actual proof only involves applications of this axiom, with z instantiated by the generators a , b , or their inverses a' or b' . Every such application corresponds to an application of AC3 rule with a conjugation by a generator or an inverse generator. We denote by **S2** a sequence of AC-tranformations obtained from S1 by replacing all contiguous sequences of conjugation rules with their compositions, effectively simplifying them into single conjugations. **S2** has a length 160. We demontsrate it below, using the following notation convention. Inverted generators a' and b' are denoted by A and B respectively. We use INV, MULT-L, MULT-R and CONJ wXw' to denote the applications of the rules R1L, R2L, R2R and a version of R3L, that is conjugation by w, respectively.

- | | |
|------------------------------------|-----------------------|
| 1. ABaBAbaBBabAb,BAbbABabaBBa | -> INV |
| 2. BaBAbbABabAba,BAbbABabaBBa | -> CONJ AbXBa |
| 3. BAbbABabAbaBa,BAbbABabaBBa | -> INV |
| 4. AbABaBAbaBBab,BAbbABabaBBa | -> MULT-L |
| 5. AbABaaBBa,BAbbABabaBBa | -> INV |
| 6. AbbAAbaba,BAbbABabaBBa | -> CONJ BaXAb |
| 7. bAAbA,BAbbABabaBBa | -> MULT-L |
| 8. bAAbAbAbbABabaBBa,BAbbABabaBBa | -> INV |
| 9. AbbABAbabBBabABaaB,BAbbABabaBBa | -> MULT-R |
| 10. AbbABAbabBBabABaaB,ABaaB | -> INV |
| 11. bAAbAbAbbABabaBBa,ABaaB | -> CONJ ABaaBXbAAba |
| 12. BAbbABabaBBabAAbA,ABaaB | -> MULT-L |
| 13. BAbbABabaBBa,ABaaB | -> CONJ BBabXBAbb |
| 14. ABabaBBaBAbb,ABaaB | -> INV |
| 15. BBabAbbABaba,ABaaB | -> MULT-L |
| 16. BBabAbbABaB,ABaaB | -> INV |
| 17. bAbabBBaBAbb,ABaaB | -> CONJ ABaBxbAba |
| 18. BBaBAbbbAba,ABaaB | -> MULT-L |
| 19. BBaBAbbbaB,ABaaB | -> CONJ bAbbXBbaB |
| 20. AbbbabBBaB,ABaaB | -> INV |
| 21. bAbbbABBBa,ABaaB | -> MULT-L |
| 22. bAbbbABBBBaaB,ABaaB | -> INV |
| 23. bAAbbbbaBBBaB,ABaaB | -> CONJ aBXba |
| 24. AbbbbaBBB,ABaaB | -> INV |
| 25. bbbABBBBaaB,ABaaB | -> MULT-L |
| 26. bbbABBBBaaB,ABaaB | -> INV |
| 27. bAAbbbbaBBB,ABaaB | -> MULT-R |
| 28. bAAbbbbaBBB,AbbbbaBBB | -> CONJ aBXba |
| 29. AbbbbaBBa,AbbbbaBBB | -> INV |
| 30. abbABBBBaa,AbbbbaBBB | -> MULT-L |
| 31. abbABBBB,AbbbbaBBB | -> INV |
| 32. bbbAbaBBa,AbbbbaBBB | -> CONJ AXa |
| 33. AbbbAbaBB,AbbbbaBBB | -> INV |
| 34. bbABaBBBaa,AbbbbaBBB | -> MULT-L |
| 35. bbABabaBBB,AbbbbaBBB | -> CONJ baBBBbbbAB |
| 36. baBABA,AbbbbaBBB | -> MULT-L |
| 37. baBAbbbaBBB,AbbbbaBBB | -> INV |
| 38. bbbABBBabAB,AbbbbaBBB | -> MULT-R |
| 39. bbbABBBabAB,AbabAB | -> INV |
| 40. baBAbbbaBBB,AbabAB | -> CONJ bABXbaB |
| 41. AbbbbaBBaB,AbabAB | -> INV |
| 42. bAbbABBBa,AbabAB | -> MULT-L |
| 43. bAbbABbAbAB,AbabAB | -> INV |
| 44. baBAbbaBBaB,AbabAB | -> CONJ bABXbaB |
| 45. AbbaBBaaB,AbabAB | -> INV |
| 46. bAAbbABBa,AbabAB | -> MULT-L |
| 47. bAAbbABabAB,AbabAB | -> INV |
| 48. baBAbabBaaB,AbabAB | -> CONJ bABXbaB |
| 49. AbaBBaaaB,AbabAB | -> INV |
| 50. bAAAbbaBA,AbabAB | -> MULT-L |
| 51. bAAAbbbAB,AbabAB | -> INV |
| 52. baBBBaaaB,AbabAB | -> CONJ aaBXbaA |
| 53. aaaBBBa,AbabAB | -> MULT-L |
| 54. aaaBBabAB,AbabAB | -> CONJ bABXbaB |
| 55. bABaaaBBa,AbabAB | -> MULT-L |
| 56. bABaaaBabAB,AbabAB | -> CONJ bABXbaB |
| 57. bAABaaaBa,AbabAB | -> MULT-L |
| 58. bAABaaaabAB,AbabAB | -> CONJ AbaaBXbaAAa |
| 59. aaabAABA,AbabAB | -> MULT-L |
| 60. aaabAabAB,AbabAB | -> CONJ AXa |
| 61. aabAABA,AbabAB | -> MULT-L |
| 62. aabAAbbAB,AbabAB | -> CONJ AXa |
| 63. abAAbbaBA,AbabAB | -> MULT-L |
| 64. abAAbbbAB,AbabAB | -> CONJ AXa |
| 65. bAAbbbaBA,AbabAB | -> MULT-L |
| 66. bAAbbbbAB,AbabAB | -> CONJ aBXba |
| 67. AbbbbaA,AbabAB | -> INV |
| 68. aaBBBba,AbabAB | -> MULT-L |
| 69. aaBBBabAB,AbabAB | -> INV |
| 70. baBAbbbaA,AbabAB | -> MULT-R |
| 71. baBAbbbaA,AbbbbaA | -> CONJ bABXbaB |
| 72. AbbbAAbab,AbbbbaA | -> INV |
| 73. bABaaBBBa,AbbbbaA | -> MULT-L |
| 74. bABaaBA,AbbbbaA | -> CONJ abAAAXaaBA |
| 75. abAAbABA,AbbbbaA | -> MULT-L |
| 76. abAAbAbbbaA,AbbbbaA | -> CONJ BaaBAXabAAb |
| 77. AbbbAAbAb,AbbbbaA | -> INV |
| 78. BaaBaBBBa,AbbbbaA | -> MULT-L |
| 79. BaaBabAA,AbbbbaA | -> CONJ AbXBa |
| 80. aBabAABA,AbbbbaA | -> MULT-L |
| 81. aBAbAAbbbbaA,AbbbbaA | -> CONJ ABAbAXaBaba |
| 82. AbbbABaba,AbbbbaA | -> INV |
| 83. aBAbabBBa,AbbbbaA | -> MULT-L |
| 84. aBAbabAA,AbbbbaA | -> CONJ abAAAXaaBA |
| 85. abABA,AbbbbaA | -> MULT-L |
| 86. abABAAbbbbaA,AbbbbaA | -> INV |
| 87. aaBBBbaBabaBA,AbbbbaA | -> MULT-R |
| 88. aaBBBbaBabaBA,BabaBA | -> INV |
| 89. abABAAbbbbaA,BabaBA | -> CONJ BabaBAXabABaB |
| 90. AbbbbaAbABab,BabaBA | -> MULT-L |
| 91. AbbbbaA,BabaBA | -> CONJ BaXAb |
| 92. bbbAAbAb,BabaBA | -> MULT-L |
| 93. bbbAAbabaBA,BabaBA | -> CONJ aBAXaba |
| 94. aBAbbbaAb,BabaBA | -> MULT-L |
| 95. aBAbbbaBabaBA,BabaBA | -> CONJ aBAXaba |
| 96. aBAbbbaAb,BabaBA | -> MULT-L |
| 97. aBBAAbbbaBA,BabaBA | -> CONJ BabbAXaBBab |
| 98. bbbabBBaB,BabaBA | -> MULT-L |
| 99. bbbabBabaBA,BabaBA | -> CONJ Bxb |
| 100. bbaBBaBAb,BabaBA | -> MULT-L |
| 101. bbaBBaaBA,BabaBA | -> CONJ Bxb |
| 102. baBBaaBab,BabaBA | -> MULT-L |
| 103. baBBaaaBA,BabaBA | -> CONJ Bxb |
| 104. aBBAaaBab,BabaBA | -> MULT-L |
| 105. aBBAaaaBA,BabaBA | -> CONJ bAXaB |
| 106. BaaaaBB,BabaBA | -> INV |
| 107. bbAAAAb,BabaBA | -> MULT-L |
| 108. bbAAAAbaBA,BabaBA | -> INV |
| 109. abABaaaBB,BabaBA | -> MULT-R |
| 110. abABaaaBB,BaaaaBB | -> CONJ aBAXabA |
| 111. BaaaBBabA,BaaaaBB | -> INV |
| 112. aBAbbAAAb,BaaaaBB | -> MULT-L |

113. aBAbbaBB, BaaaaBB	-> CONJ baBXbbAB
114. baBBaBAb, BaaaaBB	-> MULT-L
115. baBBaBaaaBB, BaaaaBB	-> CONJ AbbABXbaBBA
116. BaaaBaBBa, BaaaaBB	-> INV
117. AbbAbAAAb, BaaaaBB	-> MULT-L
118. AbbAbabb, BaaaaBB	-> CONJ BaXAb
119. bAbabbAb, BaaaaBB	-> MULT-L
120. bAbabbBaaaBB, BaaaaBB	-> CONJ bAbABXbAbAb
121. BaaaBAbAb, BaaaaBB	-> INV
122. bAbAbAAAb, BaaaaBB	-> MULT-L
123. bAbAbabb, BaaaaBB	-> CONJ baBXbAB
124. abAbAb, BaaaaBB	-> INV
125. babAbA, BaaaaBB	-> MULT-L
126. babAbAbBaaaBB, BaaaaBB	-> INV
127. bbAAAbabAbAb, BaaaaBB	-> MULT-R
128. bbAAAbabAbAb, abAbAb	-> INV
129. babAbAbBaaaBB, abAbAb	-> CONJ abAbABXbabAbAb
130. BaaaBabAbA, abAbAb	-> MULT-L
131. BaaaaBB, abAbAb	-> CONJ bXB
132. aaaaBBB, abAbAb	-> INV
133. bbbAAAA, abAbAb	-> MULT-L
134. bbbAAAbAbAb, abAbAb	-> INV
135. babAbBaaaBBB, abAbAb	-> CONJ BXB
136. abAbBaaaBB, abAbAb	-> INV
137. bbAAAbAbA, abAbAb	-> MULT-L
138. bbAAAbBaaBAb, abAbAb	-> INV
139. babAbBaaaBB, abAbAb	-> CONJ BXB
140. abAbBaaaB, abAbAb	-> INV
141. bAAAbBaaBA, abAbAb	-> MULT-L
142. bAAAbBaaBAb, abAbAb	-> INV
143. babAAAbBaaB, abAbAb	-> CONJ BXB
144. abAAAbBaaa, abAbAb	-> INV
145. AAAbBaaBA, abAbAb	-> MULT-L
146. AAAbBaaaBAb, abAbAb	-> INV
147. babAAAbBaaa, abAbAb	-> CONJ aXA
148. abAbAAAbBaa, abAbAb	-> INV
149. AAbBaaaBABA, abAbAb	-> MULT-L
150. AAbBaaaBBAB, abAbAb	-> INV
151. babbbAAAbBaa, abAbAb	-> CONJ aXA
152. ababbAAAbBaa, abAbAb	-> INV
153. AbBaaaBBABA, abAbAb	-> MULT-L
154. AbBaaaBBBAB, abAbAb	-> INV
155. babbbAAAbBaa, abAbAb	-> CONJ aXA
156. ababbAAAbBaa, abAbAb	-> INV
157. BaaaBBBABA, abAbAb	-> MULT-L
158. BaaaBBBBAB, abAbAb	-> INV
159. babbbAAAbBaa, abAbAb	-> CONJ ABXba
160. bbbBAAA, abAbAb	-> INV
aaaBBBB, abAbAb	

and inversion applied to the second (right) component of a presentation, respectively.

Similarly by **S4** we denote a sequence which matches **S2** from positions 1 to 52 and is followed by

53. aaaBBBa, AbabAB	-> Aut [a->b, b->a]
54. bbbAAAb, BabaBA	-> CONJ bXB
55. bbbBAAA, BabaBA	-> INV
56. aaaBBBB, BabaBA	-> CONJ-R bXB
57. aaaBBBB, abAbAb	

The notation $\text{Aut}[a \rightarrow b, b \rightarrow a]$ represents an automorphism of the free group that swaps the two generators. It is straightforward to demonstrate that applying automorphism transformations does not alter the AC-equivalence class when applied to presentations that are AC-equivalent to the trivial one. In [14], it was also shown that this holds for presentations AC-equivalent to any of $\text{AK}(n)$, $n > 2$.

In summary, from the first proof, we have derived four sequences of AC moves that transform the presentation P into $\text{AK}(3)$. The lengths of these sequences are 252, 160, 70, and 57, respectively, each using different subsets of elementary transformations.

3.2 Second proof

The original sequence of moves transforming P to $\text{AK}(3)$ found in [15] has the length 53 which is less than the length of any of the sequences we have extracted from the first proof. However, it is worth noting that the set of elementary AC-moves discussed in [15] differs from the standard moves we have covered so far. This set consists of the instantiations of the following templates:

AC'1 Replace some r_i by $r_i r_j^{\pm 1}$ for $i \neq j$

AC'2 Change some r_i to $g r_i g^{-1}$ where g is a generator or its inverse.

In the case of balanced presentations with two generators, the templates [**AC'1**] and [**AC'2**] give rise to 12 distinct rules. We can easily adapt the implicational translation discussed in subsection 2.1 to this case, ensuring that the analogue of Proposition 1 holds true. The logic translations of these 12 rules in Prover9 syntax are:

68. aaBBBBa, AbabAB	-> CONJ aXA
69. aaaBBBB, AbabAB	-> CONJ-R aXA
70. aaaBBBB, babABA	-> INV-R
aaaBBBB, abAbAb	

Here CONJ-R and INV-R denote a conjugation

$R(x,y) \rightarrow R(x,y * x).$	$R(x,y) \rightarrow R(x,(b' * y) * b).$
$R(x,y) \rightarrow R(x * y',y).$	$R(x,y) \rightarrow R((a * x) * a',y).$
$R(x,y) \rightarrow R(x,y * x').$	$R(x,y) \rightarrow R(x,(a * y) * a').$
$R(x,y) \rightarrow R(x * y,y).$	$R(x,y) \rightarrow R((b * x) * b',y).$
$R(x,y) \rightarrow R(x,(a' * y) * a).$	$R(x,y) \rightarrow R(x,(b * y) * b').$
$R(x,y) \rightarrow R((b' * x) * b,y).$	$R(x,y) \rightarrow R((a' * x) * a,y).$

We denote by IMG the first-order theory $T_G \cup MR$ where MR consists of the above 12 axioms encoding the modified rules. We have applied Prover9 to the task of proving the same goal as in the first proof from IMG. The proof was completed in 927.61 seconds establishing yet again AC-equivalence of presentations P and AK(3). The proof has a length of 158, while the length of the extracted sequence **S5** of AC-transformations (applications of one of the 12 rules) is 110. Its length is more than double that of the original sequence of the same rules produced in [15]. Thus, we were unable to answer the open question in [15] about whether the sequence of length 53 found there is the shortest possible sequence transforming P into AK(3).

3.3 Implementation details

For all experiments we have used LADR-Dec-2007 version of Prover9 [12] running on Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-7200U CPU @ 2.50GHz 2.71 GHz, 16 GB RAM, Windows 10 Enterprise.

4 Conclusion

We have presented alternative proofs of the stable AC-trivializability of AK(3), based on the use of automated deduction. We presented five sequences of AC-transformations derived from two different proofs demonstrating the flexibility of our method which can be adapted to encode different variants of rules. All of these may be of interest in the study of AC-reachability in general. These results also support our claim, made in [8, 9], that for all proposed potential counterexamples where non-trivial AC-simplifications were found using specialized search algorithms, AC-simplifications can also be discovered using generic theorem proving tech-

niques².

Finally, we note that in both [15] and this communication, the search conducted to establish the result on stable AC-simplifiability was actually focused on non-stable transformations. We are not aware of any computational approach that can directly search for stable AC-transformations. Our experiments with natural encodings of this task in logic, along with the use of automated theorem provers, have yet to yield any significant results. We conclude by proposing a challenge to develop computational methods for searching stable AC-transformations.

5 Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author used ChatGPT 4o mini service in order to improve readability of the manuscript. After using this service, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

References

- [1] Selman Akbulut and Robion Kirby. A potential smooth counterexample in dimension 4 to the Poincaré conjecture, the Schoenflies conjecture, and the Andrews–Curtis conjecture. *Topology*, 24(4):375–390, 1985. Available at [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0040-9383\(85\)90010-2](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0040-9383(85)90010-2). MR 87d:57024. Zbl 0584.57009.
- [2] Alexei G. Myasnikov Alexei D. Myasnikov and Vladimir Shpilrain. On the Andrews–Curtis equivalence. *Contemporary Mathematics*, 296, 2002.
- [3] J. Andrews and M.L. Curtis. Free groups and handlebodies. *Proc. Amer. Math. Soc.*, 16:192–195, 1965.

²On the other hand, novel AC-simplifications achieved through automated deduction can be found in [9, 11]

- [4] Franz Baader and Tobias Nipkow. *Term Rewriting and All That*. Cambridge University Press, New York, NY, USA, 1998.
- [5] George Havas and Colin Ramsay. Andrews-Curtis and Todd-Coxeter proof words. Technical report, in Oxford. Vol. I, London Math. Soc. Lecture Note Ser, 2001.
- [6] George Havas and Colin Ramsay. Breadth-first search and the Andrews-Curtis conjecture. *International Journal of Algebra and Computation*, 13(01):61–68, 2003.
- [7] Krzysztof Krawiec and Jerry Swan. AC-trivialization proofs eliminating some potential counterexamples to the Andrews-Curtis conjecture. Available at www.cs.put.poznan.pl/kkrawiec/wiki/uploads/Site/ACsequences.pdf, 2015.
- [8] Alexei Lisitsa. First-order theorem proving in the exploration of Andrews-Curtis conjecture. *TinyToCS*, 2, 2013.
- [9] Alexei Lisitsa. The Andrews-Curtis Conjecture, Term Rewriting and First-Order Proofs. In *Mathematical Software - ICMS 2018 - 6th International Conference, South Bend, IN, USA, July 24-27, 2018, Proceedings*, pages 343–351, 2018.
- [10] Alexei Lisitsa. Automated reasoning for the Andrews-Curtis conjecture. In *AITP 2019, Fourth Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Theorem Proving, Abstracts of the Talks April 7–12, 2019, Obergurgl, Austria*, pages 82–83, 2019.
- [11] Alexei Lisitsa. New Andrews–Curtis trivializations for Miller–Schupp group presentations. *Examples and Counterexamples*, 6:100168, 2024.
- [12] W. McCune. Prover9 and mace4. <http://www.cs.unm.edu/~mccune/prover9/>, 2005–2010.
- [13] Alexei D. Miasnikov. Genetic algorithms and the Andrews-Curtis conjecture. *International Journal of Algebra and Computation*, 09(06):671–686, 1999.
- [14] Dmitry Panteleev and Alexander Ushakov. Conjugacy search problem and the Andrews-Curtis conjecture. arxiv:1609.00325, 2016.
- [15] Ali Shehper, Anibal M. Medina-Mardones, Bartłomiej Lewandowski, Angus Gruen, Piotr Kucharski, and Sergei Gukov. What makes math problems hard for reinforcement learning: a case study. arxiv:2408.15332, 2024.
- [16] Jerry Swan, Gabriela Ochoa, Graham Kendall, and Martin Edjvet. Fitness Landscapes and the Andrews-Curtis Conjecture. *IJAC*, 22(2), 2012.